

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

**Deliverable: D1.3 Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan -
M31 Update**

15/06/2022

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D1.3		
Deliverable Title	Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update		
Due Date	31-Dec-2019	Delivery Date	01-Jan-2020
Lead Beneficiary	CITE (7)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	CITE, INAF, NKUA		
Editor(s)	Konstantinos Kakalettris (CITE); Georgios Kakalettris (CITE)		
Authors (s)	Konstantinos Kakalettris (CITE); Georgios Kakalettris (CITE); Eleni Petra (NKUA)		
Contributor (s)			
Reviewer(s)	Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA)		
Workpackage No	WP1-Management		
Version	V1.0	Stage	Approved
Version details	Revision: 82 . Last save: 2022-07-05 , 15:22 Pages: 48 . Characters: 80.084		
Distribution	Public	Type	Report
Keywords	EOSC; Risk Management; Quality Assurance; Planning; H2020;		

Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1.0	8-Jan-2020	Document version submitted to EC	K. Kakalettris	
2.0	15-Jun-2022	Updated risks table for the end of the project and beyond	K. Kakalettris	Updated §3.4 Risks. Minor updates in the rest of the document along with typos' fixing.

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

This document has been produced receiving funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the NEANIAS project Consortium and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners

that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 28 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	7
Abstract	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1. Context	9
1.2. Contents and Rationale	9
1.3. Structure of the document.....	9
2. Quality Assurance	10
2.1. Strategy	10
2.2. Responsibilities.....	11
2.3. Procedures.....	13
2.3.1. <i>Deliverables</i>	13
2.3.2. <i>Milestones</i>	18
2.3.1. <i>KPIs</i>	20
2.3.2. <i>Publications</i>	21
2.3.3. <i>Software</i>	22
2.3.4. <i>Meetings</i>	22
2.3.5. <i>Events participation</i>	24
2.3.6. <i>Training</i>	25
2.3.7. <i>Press Releases & Articles</i>	26
2.3.8. <i>Other Dissemination Material</i>	27
3. Risk Management	30
3.1. Preface.....	30
3.1.1. <i>NEANIAS particularities</i>	30
3.2. Methodology	31
3.2.1. <i>The Assets</i>	31
3.2.2. <i>Risk Analysis</i>	32
3.2.3. <i>Risk Control</i>	34
3.3. Procedures & Responsibilities	36
3.3.1. <i>Planning</i>	36
3.3.2. <i>Mitigation</i>	38
3.3.3. <i>Monitoring</i>	38
3.3.4. <i>Residual risk</i>	39
3.4. Identified Risks	39
References	47

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

List of acronyms 48

Tables of Figures & Tables

Document Figures

No table of figures entries found.

Document Tables

Table 2.1: Deliverable reviewing partners	16
Table 2.2: Milestone reviewing partners	19
Table 3.1: Probability and Impact values.	33
Table 3.2: Risk information gathered	36
Table 3.3: Current Top Ranking Identified Risks	39
The following was the initial list of highest ranked identified risks at the time of the report:Table 3.3: Initial Top Ranking Identified Risks	45

Abstract

This document is D1.3 “Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan” of NEANIAS project and its purpose is to present the overall strategy, the tools and the procedures regarding Quality Assurance and Risk Management for NEANIAS. In particular, the aim of this deliverable is to describe the mechanisms that will be employed throughout the project in order to ensure the quality level of project deliverables and outcomes.

Regarding quality assurance it defines specific policies and moreover it defines separate policies for a number of activities referring to project deliverables, milestones, research publications, meetings’ organization, events’ participation, press releases, dissemination and other outreach material, training, KPIs training etc. To be effective, on one hand it assigns nominated reviewers for contractual outcomes, such as deliverables, while on the other, it adopts minimum overhead approaches, such as open flow of information and “silent approval” policy, in areas where less critical issues may reside.

Regarding risk management, it defines the methodology to be followed, which allows risk management to be supported by non-experts, minimizing the learning curve and the risk for neglecting issues. It also defines the instruments and timeline for executing the methodology, in order to provide sufficient risk assurance for the project assets.

In the updated version of the document the list of risk is adapted to the risks that threaten the project and the sustainability of its services for the last period of the project and beyond.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

This report is deliverable D1.3 “Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update” of NEANIAS H2020 project. The report is product of the work performed in T1.3, “Quality assurance and risk management” of WP1 “Management” of the project.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

This document’s purpose is to present the overall strategy, the tools and the procedures regarding Quality Assurance and Risk Management for NEANIAS, along with the Risks that threaten the smooth accomplishment of its. The document contains essential information for managing and executing project activities and as such it is timed early in project’s lifetime (end of 2nd month of the project) and is updated before the end of the project with findings, restrictions and results of the activity, if any. In particular, this document serves as a guide for the project coordinator, in order to ensure that quality reviews will occur at appropriate points until the completion of the project, as well as a reference for all the project partners, in order to understand their responsibilities, regarding the project deliverables and outcomes. Moreover, this document establishes a framework for the project coordination team to effectively carrying out all management activities and monitor the project for current and future risks and, thus, act proactively and effectively. It is also a handbook for every member of the consortium to conduct their contractual project activities maintaining a high-quality output level, engaging into an efficient and effective collaboration scheme.

Although risks are monitored and handled continuously during the project, an update of the document is issued before the end of the project, highlighting status of risks until project’s end and beyond.

1.3. Structure of the document

The rest of this document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 presents the processes and instruments for managing **Quality Assurance** in a variety of project assets, such as deliverables, events, dissemination material, publications etc.
- Chapter 3 presents the reasoning, methodology, processes, responsibilities and tools for **Risk Management** in the course of the project.

2. Quality Assurance

2.1. Strategy

In a complex project of 20 active partners (21 in total) and 100s of internal deliverables – beside the official ones - it is essential that Quality Assurance is designed so that it covers each and every activity of the project and every kind of artifact it may produce. An item of inferior quality not only affects the overall sustainability of the project and the reputation of engaged partners and individuals but may have cascading effects in the progress of the project and its contractual obligations. The procedures described in this document will address all required activities for the smooth and effective evolution of NEANIAS project until its completion. The overall goal is to achieve and maintain (i) high-quality of the work performed and (ii) high-quality of project documentation. However, on the other hand, in a Research and Innovation Action, Quality Assurance has to be subtle, escape any bureaucratic construct that may impose a bottleneck to project activities and fairly distribute the effort to project members adding as little as possible to their work, exploiting their expertise the best way possible.

To satisfy those needs, the following elements form the basis of the Quality Assurance process of NEANIAS:

- A **Quality Assurance and Risk Management Team (QAT)** formed in the beginning of the project, supervises the whole QA process of the project and suggests
 - The Project Management Board (PMB) may modify suggestions of the QAT regarding quality assurance evaluation results, assignments etc.
 - QAT may directly report any Quality Assurance or Risk Management issue, directly to the General Assembly (GA) for further resolution.
 - The General Assembly is always the ultimate in-project decision body for Quality Assurance and Risk Management topics.
- A quality assurance process is defined for **every type of deliverable** or other **publicly delivered artifact** of the project.
 - The process is presented in the initial deliverable and was evaluated and tuned on a regular basis (bimonthly after M12) and was adapted to the nature and progress of the work around each deliverable.. Responsible for triggering the revision is the Quality Assurance Manager (QAM).
 - The process depends on the item in question and may be adapted with the intervention of QAT to fit the special needs of specific items due to their complexity or emergency.
- A **review process** is defined for selected types artifacts, mainly of contractual project deliverables and milestones, yet the process may be extended to other types of items. The review process is based around the assignment of a nominated reviewer, a strict timeline for deliberation and review of the item and finally its approval.
 - The reviewer is selected:
 - as being as less related to the artifact creation as possible; however this may not always be feasible
 - on the basis of his/her expertise
 - according to his/her availability
 - to ensure fairness of sharing reviews among project partners.
 - The reviewer may assign deputy or replacement from his/her organization at any time. The replacement has to be formally announced.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- The reviewer may kindly ask support from other consortium members for reviewing elements of a deliverable, however the review remains his/her responsibility. This review support has to be announced to the item authors/editors/creators and the QAT
- QAT may
 - review any item at any point in time, in parallel to its normal QA process.
 - assign additional reviewers to a deliverable according to the complexity of the item or the availability in each period. Additional reviewers perform such activities on a voluntarily basis.
- Reviewers are not required to edit or contribute to the quality of the item with direct effort, however this may be welcome by the item authors and/or the project. As such, the Reviewers may directly suggest or perform changes which are left to the item manager for acceptance or rejection.
- Two means of approving an item are selected depending on the nature and significance of the item:
 - **Declarative approval**, where partners need to explicitly declare their acceptance or rejection of an item. This is form of a voting process and a quorum is needed. Unless otherwise mentioned, a reasoning will be required for both acceptance and rejection statements.
 - **Silent approval**, which is the most widely suggested process in NEANIAS, where a default action is assumed (e.g. “accepted”) unless one of the members of consortium raises an objection. Any objection has to be reasoned.
- Once an item is **Rejected** there may be several manners for recovering, which depends on the stage and reason for objection.
 - If a rejection is made on the basis of specific required changes, those may be deliberated with the manager and after fixed the item may go through the process again.
 - A rejection occurring in silent approval may escalate to a declarative approval if no other solution is found after repeated deliberation steps.
 - The order of precedence of instruments in the project for approval of items is as follows:
 - Any WG < PMB < GA (< EC)
- A track of any review process is maintained in NEANIAS Project Management platform (<https://ticketing.neanias.eu/>)

2.2. Responsibilities

In the following the responsibilities of the various stakeholders is summarized.

- QAT:
 - Presents the overall QAT plan
 - Assigns the organisations for reviewing elements and tentatively may propose reviewer names
 - Proposes to PMB any Quality Assurance and Risk Management related activity
 - May introduce adhoc changes to any item QA process on the basis of complexity or emergency reasons.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- May directly address the General Assembly and any partner on any Quality Assurance and Risk Management issue (non-overridable by PMB)
- May review any deliverable and project artifact on a voluntary basis. (non-overridable by PMB)
- May assign additional reviewers (volunteers) to specific items (non-overridable by PMB)
- **PMB:**
 - Completes and disambiguates any QAT proposal.
 - Approves most QAT actions (except non-overridable)
 - Assigns or re-assigns reviewers.
 - May modify the review process according to QAT proposal or other reasons.
 - May escalate a silent approval into declarative approval.
 - May escalate any Quality Assurance or Risk Management issue to the GA.
 - Silently or deliberately approves any project artifact.
- **Editor / Lead beneficiary**
 - Coordinates authors, contributors and other beneficiaries to perform the actions that lead to the completion of the artifact.
 - Triggers the review process that corresponds to the artifact type both in communication and project management platform instruments.
 - Requests any exceptional handling from the QAT reasoning on the specialties of the artifact.
 - Acts on the side of the artifact as correspondent for the entire quality assurance process. Routes reviewers' suggestions to the item co-authors/contributors.
 - May request escalation of an issue via the PMB and subsequently GA.
- **Reviewers (& reviewers' deputies)**
 - Review an item according to the review process established and provide detailed feedback on quality improvement actions that are needed.
 - May voluntarily contribute to the quality of an artifact with specific editing of the item in question.
 - May invite supplementary volunteer reviewers for specific elements of an artifact, after notifying the QAT and the Editor.
 - May replace themselves with other members of their organization to confront any expertise or availability issues.
- **Authors/Contributors**
 - Author the deliverable under editor's coordination
 - Respond to reviewers' requests by complying or rejecting those with sufficient reasoning.
- **WP Leaders**
 - May request exceptional handling of deliverables of their workpackages due to specialties in urgency, significance and complexity or prior delays.
- **Project Coordinator**
 - May review any project item. The review must be announced to the deliverable editor and follow and augment the normal review process (i.e. on the same timeline). The PC is responsible for resolving any review conflict in case such arise.
- **General Assembly**

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Silently or deliverable approves any project artifact before publication or submission.
- May override any prior decision taken at PMB or GA.
- May accept a formerly rejected artifact.
- Project Manager
 - Coordinates the PMB
 - In case of contractual deliverables, performs the actions of submission to the EC, engaging the Administration and Management Support Team of the project.

2.3. Procedures

In the following section the procedure for Quality Assurance of each item type produced by the project is highlighted.

2.3.1. Deliverables

2.3.1.1. Types of Deliverables

The types of deliverables foreseen are

- **R**: documents of any type such as work reports, design documents, best practices documents etc
- **DEM**: demos, pilots, prototype etc
- **DEC**: websites, press releases, media actions, webinars, multimedia etc
- **OTHER**: software, datasets, etc.

The policy of the project is that all deliverables will be presented to the EC as a document.

- In the case of deliverables of type **R**, the deliverable itself is the document submitted to the EC.
- In the case of all other types of deliverables (**DEM, DEC, OTHER**) a short report of a few pages (as few as one page of content) has to be presented by the lead beneficiary. This short report shall contain a descriptive summary of the actual deliverable and evidence for its existence and delivery. This short report may present one or more of the following project deliverables/ outcomes:
 - Links
 - Websites
 - Events
 - Software code
 - On-line software
 - On-line live documents
 - Datasets
 - DOIs
 - Publications
 - Datasets
 - Short descriptive and/or summary statements about the items delivered
 - Datasets
 - Demos
 - Events
 - Training sessions
 - Screenshots of the delivered dynamic artifacts if applicable

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- web sites
 - software
 - dataset visualisations
- Graphic snapshots
 - Videos
 - Webinars
 - Presentations
 - Posters
- Photos
 - Events
- etc.

A special template has been prepared for deliverables of type R, while a shorter one is introduced for reporting on deliverables of type DEC, DEM and OTHER.

2.3.1.2. Procedure Details

Important Note: Deliverable confidentiality rating must be respected by all engaged parties during all stages of the review process.

The process is as follows:

- Reviewer assignment
 - Assignment is performed within first two months of the project. Assignment of reviewers of M2 deliverables is performed in M1 during project's Kick Off meeting.
 - *All required assignments have been already done for all NEANIAS deliverables by the time of completion of this document and have been announced to the consortium on the shared workspace.*
 - A reviewers table is presented by QAT based on partner's project share and expertise.
 - PMB nominates reviewers under the suggestions made by the Project Manager.
 - Reviewers
 - never come from lead beneficiary of a deliverable
 - have the competences to review the deliverable
 - are preferably not members of the authoring group (not always feasible)
- Deliverable reviewing:
 - The editor examines the review timeline and deliberates with primary reviewer, in order to identify that 60 productive calendar days are available (i.e. no common vacation time is included). If needed requests an extension of the period to more than 60 days.
 - No approval is needed by other actors for extending the review period.
 - The editor sends Table of Content (TOC) to reviewer: max **sixty (60) days** before deadline.
 - TOC must be at least two levels deep.
 - One paragraph per 2nd level section of the TOC needs to be supplied.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- The TOC is sent via the Project Workspace in the proper location as foreseen by the respective WP (<https://workspace.neanias.eu/>). The deliverable will be exchanged in the same area among all reviewing entities.
 - Notifies QAT on the launch of the process.
 - QAT may assign additional reviewers.
 - Additional reviewers are announced to the Editor and the primary reviewer.
 - Reviewer(s) comment(s) on TOC: within **seven (7) days**.
 - Shall provide a formal statement on the review step result. One single review log file is maintained next to the deliverable, on the workspace for all reviewers.
 - The editor, if needed, responds to reviewer(s) comments and deliberates for the final TOC (within 2 days)
 - Primary reviewers' comments are to be handled with priority.
 - Editor and authors complete the deliverable: within **twenty (20) days**.
 - The deliverable submitted to reviewer(s)
 - Reviewer(s) provide(s) feedback to the editor: within **seven (7) days**.
 - May supply optional edits that he/she may voluntarily perform
 - Shall provide a formal statement on the review step result in the review log file.
 - Editor responds to reviewer(s) feedback. Deliberation may follow within **seven (7) days**.
 - At the end, the editor submits the deliverable to the QAT for next steps.
 - QAT validates the process and may launch final deliberation with editor and reviewer(s) (up to 7 days)
 - At any time within this period the QAT submits the deliverable to PMB and the GA.
 - PMB silently approves the deliverable: within **five (5) days**.
 - GA silently approves the deliverable, in parallel to PMB: within **seven (7) days**.
 - Upon approval within **two (2) days** the Project Manager passes the document to the Administration and Management Support Team, for notifying the EC (if needed).
 - A few days of amortization are foreseen in order to align to weekdays and minor delays
 - If reasonable objections occur, the milestone is delayed, and further corrective actions are planned by the PMB and the QAT.
- The role of the reviewer is as already highlighted in §2.2 "Responsibilities", yet the following aspects are highlighted here:
 - Must:
 - Reject or approve the document (even with reservations)
 - Create a new or update an existing review log document.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Provide a short note on the review activities and the evaluation of the document in the review log document.
 - Remain solely responsible for the outcome of his/her review.
- May:
 - Directly perform changes on syntactic, grammatic or other authoring changes
 - Suggest changes of the document that are performed by editor
 - Suggest changes of the document that are performed by the reviewer and accepted by the editor
 - Assign the review of parts of the document to deputies depending on availability, urgency and expertise.
- May not:
 - Unreasonably reject a document or part of its content, without justification

2.3.1.3. Deliverable reviewing partners assignments

Table 2.1: Deliverable reviewing partners

LABEL	TITLE	WP ID	DELIVERY MONTH	LEAD	REVIEWER
D1.1	Project collaboration space and communication instruments	WP1	2	NKUA	JACOBSUNI
D1.2	Project procedures and instruments	WP1	2	NKUA	INAF
D1.3	Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan	WP1	2	CITE	ATHENA
D1.4	Innovation and IPR Management - Open Access policy report	WP1	4	INNOMINE	INCITES
D1.5	Data management plan	WP1	6	ATHENA	SZTAKI
D1.6	Periodic Report (mid-term)	WP1	18	NKUA	RICOH
D1.7	Whitepaper: Onboarding EOSC hub: best practices and lessons learnt	WP1	20	SZTAKI	INCITES
D1.8	Final Report	WP1	36	NKUA	SZTAKI
D1.9	Periodic Report (final)	WP1	36	NKUA	INAF
D2.1	Underwater Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications & Software development Plan	WP2	6	AMU	MEEEO
D2.2	Underwater Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications	WP2	25	AMU	ALTEC
D2.3	Underwater Thematic Services Release #1	WP2	12	NKUA	CITE
D2.4	Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1	WP2	13	UBREMEN	GARR
D2.5	Underwater Thematic Services Release #2	WP2	23	CORONIS	CITE
D2.6	Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #2	WP2	24	UBREMEN	GARR
D2.7	Underwater Thematic Services Release #3	WP2	30	NKUA	CITE
D2.8	Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #3	WP2	31	UBREMEN	GARR
D2.9	Underwater Thematic Services Assessment Report	WP2	34	NKUA	JACOBSUNI
D3.1	Atmospheric Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications & Software development Plan	WP3	6	UBIWHERE	INAF

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

LABEL	TITLE	WP ID	DELIVERY MONTH	LEAD	REVIEWER
D3.2	Atmospheric Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications	WP3	25	UBIWHERE	INNOMINE
D3.3	Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #1	WP3	12	ATHENA	JACOBSUNI
D3.4	Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services #1	WP3	13	UNIMIB	INAF
D3.5	Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #2	WP3	23	ATHENA	JACOBSUNI
D3.6	Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services #2	WP3	24	UNIMIB	INAF
D3.7	Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #3	WP3	30	NKUA	JACOBSUNI
D3.8	Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services #3	WP3	31	UNIMIB	INAF
D3.9	Atmospheric Thematic Services Assessment Report	WP3	34	UBIWHERE	SZTAKI
D4.1	Space Research Services Report on requirements, Specifications & Software development Plan	WP4	6	ALTEC	UBIWHERE
D4.2	Space Research Services Report on requirements, Specification	WP4	25	ALTEC	CORONIS
D4.3	Space Thematic Services Release #1	WP4	12	INAF	NKUA
D4.4	Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services #1	WP4	13	JACOBSUNI	UNIMIB
D4.5	Space Thematic Services Release #2	WP4	23	UNIMIB	NKUA
D4.6	Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services #2	WP4	24	JACOBSUNI	UNIMIB
D4.7	Space Thematic Services Release #3	WP4	30	UNIMIB	NKUA
D4.8	Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services #3	WP4	31	INAF	UNIMIB
D4.9	Space Thematic Services Assessment Report	WP4	34	ALTEC	CORONIS
D5.1	Business innovation cases analysis & activity planning	WP5	14	INNOMINE	NKUA
D5.2	Report on business innovation cases services implementation (interim)	WP5	16	UBIWHERE	INCITES
D5.3	Business innovation cases software release #1	WP5	16	CITE	SZTAKI
D5.4	Open Call for Innovation	WP5	18	INNOMINE	NKUA
D5.5	Open Call for innovation evaluation report	WP5	21	ATHENA	ALTEC
D5.6	Invited innovation cases boarding gap analysis & activity planning	WP5	25	CITE	UBIWHERE
D5.7	Business innovation cases software release #2	WP5	32	CITE	NKUA
D5.8	Business innovation cases onboarding activities report	WP5	34	MEE0	RICOH
D5.9	Report on business innovation cases services implementation (final)	WP5	34	INNOMINE	ATHENA
D6.1	Core services architecture, design principles and specifications report – Implementation Plan	WP6	6	INAF	UBREMEN
D6.2	Core services Release #1	WP6	10	CITE	MEE0
D6.3	Core services software release report #1	WP6	10	JACOBSUNI	UOP
D6.4	Core services architecture, design principles and specifications report – Implementation Plan (update)	WP6	18	INAF	UBREMEN
D6.5	Core services Release #2	WP6	21	INAF	MEE0
D6.6	Core services software release report #2	WP6	21	SZTAKI	UOP

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

LABEL	TITLE	WP ID	DELIVERY MONTH	LEAD	REVIEWER
D6.7	Core services Release #3	WP6	28	CITE	MEE0
D6.8	Core services software release report #3	WP6	28	UOP	UOP
D6.9	NEANIAS best practices for interoperability and reuse	WP6	17	MEE0	ALTEC
D7.1	Delivery activities methodology and plan	WP7	5	GARR	ATHENA
D7.2	Software delivery infrastructure and tools	WP7	6	GARR	CORONIS
D7.3	Software Assessment Methodology	WP7	8	SZTAKI	NKUA
D7.4	Infrastructures integration report (interim)	WP7	16	SZTAKI	UBREMEN
D7.5	Operation Activities Report (interim)	WP7	18	GARR	NOA
D7.6	Training & user onboarding activities report (interim)	WP7	18	INAF	EUNICE
D7.7	Infrastructures integration report (final)	WP7	34	SZTAKI	UBREMEN
D7.8	Operation Activities Report (final)	WP7	36	GARR	NOA
D7.9	Training & user onboarding activities report (final)	WP7	36	INAF	EUNICE
D8.1	EOSC integration plan	WP8	9	SZTAKI	CITE
D8.2	EOSC service model report	WP8	14	ATHENA	SZTAKI
D8.3	EOSC integration plan (final)	WP8	22	ATHENA	CITE
D8.4	EOSC integration activities report (interim)	WP8	25	ATHENA	INNOMINE
D8.5	EOSC integration activities report (final)	WP8	32	ATHENA	INNOMINE
D8.6	Best practices for service onboarding the EOSC hub	WP8	34	ATHENA	CORONIS
D9.1	Exploitation plan	WP9	5	INNOMINE	AMU
D9.2	Sustainability and assessment methodology	WP9	8	INNOMINE	ATHENA
D9.3	Draft business plan	WP9	18	INCITES	EUNICE
D9.4	Best practices for sustainable services on EOSC	WP9	34	INCITES	ALTEC
D9.5	NEANIAS business perspective assessment report	WP9	32	INCITES	INAF
D9.6	NEANIAS sustainability report	WP9	36	INCITES	NKUA
D10.1	Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Draft)	WP10	2	RICOH	ATHENA
D10.2	Project web site	WP10	2	RICOH	NKUA
D10.3	Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report	WP10	18	RICOH	CITE
D10.4	Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)	WP10	18	RICOH	INAF
D10.5	NEANIAS open event	WP10	32	RICOH	INAF
D10.6	Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report	WP10	36	RICOH	AMU

2.3.2. Milestones

2.3.2.1. Details

The procedure for milestone's quality assurance simpler than the one adopted for Deliverables reviewing. The differences are as follows:

- The **two (2) months** before the milestone deadline, the lead beneficiary submits to the reviewer and the QAT the short document - a special template is provided for partners to use - that covers:

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- The estimated date the milestone will be reached
- The means for verification
- The reviewer posts back any comments on the milestone status and validation means within **one (1) week**.
- If such suggestions occur, the lead beneficiary needs to respond handling or rejecting any suggestions within **two (2) weeks**.
- The lead beneficiary submits to the reviewer the final notice on completion of the milestone **two (2) weeks** before the milestone deadline.
- The reviewer posts back any comments on the milestone status and validation means within **three (3) days**.
- If such suggestions occur, the lead beneficiary needs to respond handling or rejecting any suggestions within **three (3) days**.
- The reviewer passes the final approval to the PMB and GA for any further action and silent approval,
 - Both entities have **three (4) days** to raise any objection.
 - The QAT is also notified.
- Upon silent approval within **two (2) days** the Project Manager passes the document to the Administration and Management Support Team, for notifying the EC (if needed).
- If reasonable objections occur, the milestone is delayed, and further corrective actions are planned by the PMB and the QAT.

2.3.2.2. Milestone reviewing partners assignments

Table 2.2: Milestone reviewing partners

LABEL	NAME	INVOLVED WPs	MONTH	LEAD	REVIEW
MS1	Project Kick-Off	ALL	1	NKUA	ATHENA
MS2	Coordination & collaboration instruments establishment	WP1, WP10	2	ATHENA	CITE
MS3	System & business cases definition	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9	6	INNOMINE	UBIWHERE
MS4	Proof of concept showcasing	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9, WP10	14	CITE	NKUA
MS5	Mid-term Review	WP1, WP10, ALL	18	NKUA	INAF
MS6	Integrated showcasing	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8	25	INAF	CORONIS
MS7	Final Deployment	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8	32	SZTAKI	JACOBSUNI
MS8	Assessment Completion	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9, WP10	34	INCITES	MEEO
MS9	Project End	ALL	36	NKUA	ATHENA

2.3.1. KPIs

2.3.1.1. Details

Regarding the process of quality assurance for project's KPIs the following occur:

- KPI assignment:
 - A team consisting of Project Manager, SSC Coordinator and Outreach Manager introduces a KPI assignment list.
 - The team consults WP leaders and Technical Manager
 - Each KPI is assigned to one individual.
 - The individual person is appointed by the PMB following an initial proposal of the PM.
 - Each KPI may be broken down to additional sub KPIs
 - Each sub KPI is assigned to one individual too.
 - For each KPI and sub KPI a reviewer is assigned.
 - The PMB will approve the KPI assignment and review list.
 - The KPI assignment process needs to be **finalized by M4**.
 - Project management will track all KPIs assignments in the project management platform after the delivery of the list.
- KPI handling
 - Each KPI responsible presents an estimated timeline for the KPI indicating major points that the KPI will substantially progress to its final target. The timeline is maintained on the project management platform and activity tickets are added for each internal milestone.
 - Each KPI responsible may apply a further break down of a KPI.
 - KPI responsible may perform further assignments to individual partners and members of the consortium, assigning specific objectives and target values.
 - In case an objection exists in due time, this will be escalated to the PMB for resolution.
 - All partners contribute to the KPI updates with activities performed.
 - Any contribution to a KPI shall be followed by a brief description of the contribution, w.r.t. to its timing, sizing and validation means.
 - KPI updates are performed on the Project Management Platform, using platform's tools (i.e. issue comments and target value update).
 - KPI updates by partners are communicated to the KPI responsible both:
 - before the achievement (as an intention to)
 - maximum one (1) week after the achievement.
- KPI observation and reviewing
 - KPI reviewers validate the progress of KPIs on a periodic basis. The default periodic validation is on a **quarterly basis**.
 - All project boards (QAT, SSC, PMB, OTF, UB) may review KPIs at any time.
 - In case deviations from expectancies are observed, those shall be communicated to project's decision-making boards, such as the PMB or escalated to the GA in order for action to be taken.

2.3.1.1. KPI partner assignments

A table presenting KPI assignment per partner will be presented here at M6 of the project.

2.3.2. Publications

The content of every publication must be approved by the QAT. The publications must be relevant to NEANIAS project and associated with one of its deliverables. All IPR aspects agreed among consortium members as well as the following time plan towards the publication must be accepted.

- Before submission
 - The author announces the intension of publication to the **Outreach Task Force**
 - Submission of targeted journal/conference with short description and authors at least **seven (7) days** before the submission deadline of the paper to be reviewed
 - Description of Open Access Measures to be taken is made.
 - Outreach Task Force may appoint reviewer for consulting on specific elements of a publication.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves publication within **three (3) workdays**.
 - If objections on content are made those are discussed with authors and if no solution is found the issue is escalated directly to GA.
 - Announcement of the case and process to QAT by Outreach Task Force.
- Upon submission:
 - Author submits the draft publication to the Outreach Task Force: within **seven (7) days**.
 - Any further or new objections may be raised here and notified to the editors.
 - Outreach Task Force may appoint reviewer for consulting on specific elements of a publication.
- Upon acceptance:
 - Author notifies Outreach Task Force on the acceptance.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves the publication with **seven (7) days**.
 - If objections on content are made those are discussed with authors and if no solution is found the issue is escalated directly to GA.
- Upon final submission:
 - Author submits of pre-camera-ready publication to the Outreach Task Force at least **seven (7) days** before deadline.
 - The document should be quite close to the final camera-ready one.
 - Outreach Task Force validates the publication regarding:
 - Project reference text
 - Compliance with prior agreement(s)
 - Outreach Task Force may appoint reviewer(s) for consulting on specific elements of a publication.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves the pre-camera-ready document within **three (3) working days**.
 - If objections on content are made those are discussed with authors and if no solution is found the issue is escalated directly to GA.
- General Principles:

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Partners must restrict their publication content to the parts they are working on otherwise they should be extremely brief in presenting other's work, providing sufficient references.
- If partners are revealing prototypical work of other partners, the latter ones should be included as coauthors and approve the publication and its contents. The ordering of authors should be decided among partners.
- Partners whose work is shared in the publication with a substantial role in the scientific and technological should be invited as co-authors

2.3.3. Software

- Software quality assurance procedure will be defined by WP7 and included in this document at subsequent updates.
- The process shall ensure:
 - At least two levels of acceptable software quality labels
 - Method for validation of software build and delivery outcome by project technical team.
 - Method for software validating by its end users and in particular engagement of the User Board in the acceptance of software and services.
 - Method for validating TRL of the software.
 - Method for approving NEANIAS service inclusion into EOSC.

2.3.4. Meetings

The following are the elements and process for Meetings quality assurance.

- For each meeting a host and a manager are assigned.
 - The host and the manager may not be the same organization.
 - The meeting host has to accommodate meeting requirements w.r.t. infrastructure, space etc.
 - The meeting manager has to coordinate agenda, participation and meeting tracking material delivery.
- Project meetings are classified as
 - Planned: Meetings foreseen by project's DOA and the environment it operates.
 - Exceptional: Meetings that emerge as a result of the progress of work or external factors.
 - Urgent: Meetings required to confront specific urgent challenges or grab sudden opportunities that may emerge.
- Project meetings may be:
 - Physical: when the majority of project's partners are planned to be physically present. Electronic means presence may be supported partially or fully, depending on the premise.
 - Electronic: when the meeting takes place on a web conference platform offered by one of project's infrastructure partners.
- Best practices:

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- If major thematic or other events are held and combined partner presence is observed, cohosting project thematic or plenary meetings is considered a good practice.
- Rationale: Must conform to projects workplan and associated foreseen meetings or reasonably extend those.
- Pre-meeting actions:
 - Venue
 - Selected at least **two (2) months** prior to the meeting for the ones with physical presence; 2 weeks for electronic meetings
 - An overview agenda must be supplied to intended participants in due time
 - For physical meetings:
 - at least **one (1) month** before a planned or exceptional meeting
 - at least **one (1) week** before an urgent meeting
 - For electronic meetings
 - at least **two (2) weeks** before a planned or exceptional meeting
 - at least **two (2) days** before an urgent meeting.
 - A detailed agenda must be presented
 - For physical meetings:
 - at least **two (2) weeks** before a planned or exceptional meeting
 - at least **two (2) days** before an urgent meeting
 - For electronic meetings
 - at least **three (3) days** before a planned or exceptional meeting
 - at least **one (1) day** before an urgent meeting.
 - Participants list at partner level must be 90% ready:
 - **One (1) month** for physical meetings or **two (2) weeks** for urgent ones
 - **One (1) week** for electronic meetings or **three (3) days** for urgent ones
 - Participants list at person level must be 90% ready:
 - **Two (2) weeks** for physical meetings or **one (1) week** for urgent ones
 - **Three (3) days** for electronic meetings or **one (1) day** for urgent ones
 - For exceptional and urgent meetings, the aforementioned timeline is presented in detail along with the declaration of the meeting requirement.
 - The meeting manager has to
 - create a workspace folder for the meeting where all pre- /on/ post-meeting material is collected.
 - Invite participants to contribute with presentations and material.
- On-meeting actions:
 - The meeting manager:
 - Launch a minute document for each part of the meeting.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Assign a minutes' author for each section in case a meeting is not a Board/WP/Task meeting, in which case the responsibility flows to the respective manager)
 - Invite partners to manage the shared minutes document.
- Board / WP / Task Leader:
 - Must assign a minutes' author from the Board/WP/Task context the meeting is performed in.
- Participants:
 - Declare their presence in indicated minutes documents and papers.
 - Upload their presentations onto appointed workspace folder.
 - Contribute in minutes documents during and post meeting time.
- Meeting manager must assemble post meeting material from contributions and collaborative editing performed during the meeting:
 - Participants list (on a daily basis if applicable)
 - Minutes document (as maintained in meeting subsections)
 - Presentations performed
 - To Do list (s):
 - Global (if applicable)
 - Per section (if applicable)

2.3.5. Events participation

The participation of project partners to an event must be economic, impactful and strictly related to the activities and interest of the project. As such Quality Assurance foresees the following process:

- Before application to participating and event, by project partner:
 - Interested partner(s) submit to the Outreach Task Force at least **two (2) weeks** before application deadline an event plan including
 - Objective and expected results w.r.t the project
 - Relevance to the project
 - Subject of the event and participation
 - Targeted audience description and sizing
 - Estimated costs for the project
 - Any additional support required
 - Event quality evaluation method (if applicable)
 - Outreach Task Force validates that the dissemination guidelines of EC and NEANIAS are respected.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves the application within **one (1) week**, otherwise may raise concerns on relevance, cost or even suggest additional partners contribution.
 - May redirect decision to the PMB.
 - May request contribution by other team members.
 - May request augmenting or otherwise revising the participation application.
- Upon application:

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Interested partners submit to Outreach Task Force of the application information, within **three (2) days** from application.
- Outreach Task Force may distribute the application to any related partner or member of the consortium team for comments.
- Objections/comments may be raised by Outreach Task Force Members until **two (2) weeks** before the event (depending on the nature of the comment/objection)
- Before participation:
 - Submission of draft event material to Outreach TF at least **one (1) week** before material delivery
 - The material need not be final one but should be enough to identify the content of the participation.
 - Objections/comments may be raised by Outreach Task Force Members at reasonable time before the event.
- After participation:
 - Event participant(s) deliver final event material to Outreach Task Force and distribute it to the project partners
 - Event participant(s) present event evaluation data to Outreach Task Force for further analysis.
 - Event participant(s) present the approximate total cost of the event participation per participant partner to the Outreach Task Force and the PMB.
- A template for event participation is distributed in Templates area of project workspace.

2.3.6. Training

The participation in or organization of a training event by project partners must be economic, impactful and strictly related to the activities and interest of the project. As such Quality Assurance foresees the following process:

- Before organization / participation to event, by project partner:
 - Interested partner(s) submit to the Outreach Task Force at least **two (2) weeks** before application deadline (if applicable) an event plan including
 - Objective and expected results w.r.t the project
 - Relevance to the project
 - Subject of the event and participation
 - Targeted audience description and sizing
 - Estimated costs for the project
 - Any additional support required
 - Training quality evaluation method (mandatory for project organized events)
 - Outreach Task Force validates that the dissemination guidelines of EC and NEANIAS are respected, if applicable.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves the application within **one (1) week**, otherwise may raise concerns on relevance, cost or even suggest additional partners contribution.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- May redirect decision to the PMB.
 - May request contribution by other team members.
 - May request augmenting or otherwise revising the proposal.
- Upon application (applies to training events cohosted with other events or organized in the context of other events):
 - Interested partners submit to Outreach Task Force the application information, within **three (2) days** from application.
 - Outreach Task Force may distribute the application to any related partner or member of the consortium team for comments.
 - Objections/comments may be raised by Outreach Task Force Members until **two (2) weeks** before the event (depending on the nature of the comment/objection)
- Before participation:
 - Submission of draft training material to Outreach TF at least **one (1) week** before material delivery
 - The material need not be final but should be enough to identify the content of the training.
 - Objections/comments may be raised by Outreach Task Force Members at reasonable time before the event.
- After participation:
 - Event participant(s) deliver final training material to Outreach Task Force and distribute it to the project partners
 - Event participant(s) present training evaluation data to Outreach Task Force for further analysis.
 - Event participant(s) present the approximate total cost of the event participation per participant partner to the Outreach Task Force and the PMB.
- A template for event participation (applies to training events too) is distributed in Templates area of project workspace.

2.3.7. Press Releases & Articles

Press releases and articles (e.g. blog posts) are created in three manners:

- Centrally to the project by the WP10 participants collaborating on the preparation of a press release
- By appointed project partner on behalf of the entire project.
- By individual partners for use in more confined yet public areas such as web sites, social media, local press, fora etc.

In all cases a press release must follow the following principles:

- Adhere to project guidelines on the process, means and publicity.
- Respect partner representation in accordance to their contribution and position in the project.
- Apply EU rules with respect to dissemination / publicity.
- The overall process of a press release or article is as follows: Before authoring (optional step)

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- The author announces the intension of publication to the **Outreach Task Force**, along with any information concerning the reuse and reproduction of the content in the item.
- The author may request appointing a reviewer to the material or the Outreach Task Force may appoint reviewer for consulting on specific elements of material.
- Outreach Task Force silently approves creation of material within **one (1) week**
 - If objections on content are made those are discussed with authors and if no solution is found the issue is escalated directly to GA.
- If the material is instructed and/or collectively handled by WP10 then a reviewer is assigned by the Outreach Task Force.
- Before publication:
 - The author presents the item to the Outreach Task Force at least **one (1) week** before the publication, along with any information concerning the reuse and reproduction of the content in the item.
 - If an external deadline applies the author must take precaution to let enough time for project's processes to execute.
 - If an external deadline applies the author may submit a draft publication to the Outreach Task Force, that is as close as possible to the final artifact.
 - The author may request appointing a reviewer to the material or the Outreach Task Force may appoint reviewer for consulting on specific elements of material.
 - The Outreach Task Force may share the item to the rest of the project or selected partners for consultation.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves creation of material within **one (1) week**.
 - If objections on content are made those are discussed with authors and if no solution is found the issue is escalated directly to GA.
- After publication
 - The author delivers to the Outreach Task Force the publication material and along with all information about reuse, referencing and publication.
 - Outreach Task Force presents the item to the project via the shared Workspace.

NOTE: Press Releases and Articles authored by individual partners may be stressing, or even entirely focus on the role of a single partner in particular areas of the project. This is well acceptable once no false claims on other's work are made.

2.3.8. Other Dissemination Material

Other dissemination material, such as posters, graphics, cards, templates etc. is created in three manners:

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Centrally to the project by the WP10 participants collaborating on the preparation of dissemination material
- By appointed project partner on behalf of the entire project
- By individual partners for use in more confined public or private areas such as events, web sites, social media, local press, fora etc.

In all cases dissemination material must follow the following principles:

- Adhere to project guidelines on the process, means and publicity.
- Respect partner representation in accordance to their contribution and position in the project.
- Apply EU rules with respect to dissemination / publicity

The overall process for quality assurance of such content is as follows:

- Before creation (optional step)
 - The creator announces the intension to the **Outreach Task Force**, along with any information concerning the reuse and reproduction of the content in the item (if applicable).
 - The author may request appointing a reviewer to the material or the Outreach Task Force may appoint reviewer for consulting on specific elements of material.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves creation of material within **one (1) week**.
 - If objections on content are made those are discussed with authors and if no solution is found the issue is escalated directly to GA.
 - If the material is instructed and/or collectively handled by WP10 then a reviewer is assigned by the Outreach Task Force.
- Before public use:
 - The creator presents the item to the Outreach Task Force at least **one (1) week** before the public use of the content, along with any information concerning the reuse and reproduction of the content in the item.
 - If an external deadline applies the author must take precaution to let enough time for project's processes to execute.
 - If an external deadline applies the author may submit a draft version of the material to the Outreach Task Force, that is as close as possible to the final artifact.
 - The author may request appointing a reviewer to the material or the Outreach Task Force may appoint reviewer for consulting on specific elements of material.
 - The Outreach Task Force may share the item to the rest of the project or selected partners for consultation.
 - Outreach Task Force silently approves creation of material within **one (1) week**.
 - If objections on content are made those are discussed with authors and if no solution is found the issue is escalated directly to GA.
- After use and/or publication

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- The author delivers to the Outreach Task Force the publication material and along with all information about reuse, referencing and publication.
- Outreach Task Force presents the item to the project via the shared Workspace.

NOTE: Dissemination material authored by individual partners may be stressing, or even entirely focus on the role of a single partner in particular areas of the project, yet remaining aligned to the activities and objectives of the project. This is well acceptable once no false claims on other's work are made.

3. Risk Management

3.1. Preface

The risk management activities within NEANIAS have the objective to avoid or minimize the impact of potentially possible, but unlikely or unforeseen, external or internal events that may affect the likelihood to achieve the targeted NEANIAS outcome in scheduled time, required quality and/or foreseen cost.

Based also on the risks outlined in the DoW, the risk management process is repeated at regular intervals during the project execution towards proactive actions and control of risk factors. NEANIAS risk management activities implement mitigation wherever and whenever necessary. For sure, not all events can be foreseen but the considered, here, continuous monitoring shall catch all events that endanger the progress and success of NEANIAS or the quality its outcomes.

3.1.1. NEANIAS particularities

NEANIAS project is a relative large-scale **Research Project**, with substantial portion of **Information Technology** (IT) elements and as such carries all the specialties and risks of projects of the two kinds. Indicatively, one source¹ states that over 20% of software IT projects completely fail, while among the rest only an approximation of 25% fully accomplishes its achievements. Any project in between is either failing in terms of cost or time or under-delivering. A more recent approach² shows that up to 5-15% of systems delivered are totally abandoned while close to their delivery, while about 30% succeed their purposes. The last observation shows that even the term “failure” is not as fixed as one could expect it to be. Research oriented projects have one additional risk factor: walking on boundary of state-of-the-art has an inherent increased failure probability.

The following points provide reasons which expose the common failures of similar projects as compared to, other sector’s project:

- Software and research are abstract entities that may be perceived differently by different recipients which impacts their alignment with project’s course and results.
- A large-scale IT and research project is always dissimilar to other large-scale IT projects in several details, i.e. previous success steps cannot guarantee success in the next project.
- There is no algorithmic roadmap for transforming requirements to software, which implies certain limitations to the success project roadmap establishment.
- The ingredients of the implementation of a research and IT software project cannot be precisely defined before the execution of the project, in order to limit the risk, which becomes even more complex in modern ecosystems with numerous internal and external dependencies, like the ones assumed by the NEANIAS.
- Requirements and expectancies of recipients of project outcomes evolve in time as the environment of the project and the understanding of the recipients evolves.

¹ Source: Microsoft MSDN MOF Definition Presentations (2002)

² IEEE Spectrum Online (2006)

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Research projects include “Inherent Risks” i.e. risks that are outside the control of the process and such may be the infeasibility of an endeavor, which though is significantly reduced in the case of NEANIAS project, as it builds on established technologies.

In order to minimize specific risk of similar projects, agile methodologies have emerged, however even those focus on preventing specific failures, assuming others are less impactful for the overall project success.

Another challenge is the quantification of the Assets, the risks, likely-hoods and impact of a project.

Deviating from risk management practices found in other types of projects, and due to similar reasons with a potential for overall project failure, both the prediction and estimation of risks is hard and usually not quantifiable. Furthermore, combined risk possibilities are harder to resolve and quantify, since risks are often not totally independent among themselves.

In context described up to now, we actually use the term *risk* to label any incident that might occur and in one way or another cause a deviation of NEANIAS outcome from its expected one. This deviation can be identified in terms of

- functional deviation of the produced system (e.g. lack of features)
- or non-functional deviation of the produced system (e.g. performance)
- timeline extension
- monetary extension (in terms of cost, not claims)

The impact might span several directions, e.g. financial (direct or indirect), ethical, or legal.

Two significant challenges in evaluating a risk, once identified, are:

- (a) To translate the impact(s) on a comparative term basis (e.g. monetary impact).
- (b) To approximate the likelihood of the occurrence of a risk.

The methodology adopted attempts to simplify the evaluation and the metrics associated with it, so that those can be maintained by non-experts in risk analysis, yielding valuable results in the course of the project.

3.2. Methodology

3.2.1. The Assets

Risk has no cost if it does not jeopardize some kind of “Assets”. These Assets can vary from project to project and can usually translated to monetary terms, although this is not always so straightforward. On the other hand, depending on the interest of the project the impact on the Assets and the recovery / avoidance costs can also be difficult to quantify depending on their nature and the risk. Typically, money and time can be used interchangeably, however this is again not straightforward. For example, increasing the expenditure does not indefinitely reduce time, etc.

That which could be quite feasible to identify in other projects, i.e. their assets, is still complex in NEANIAS. There is a magnitude of Assets produced, most of which are hard to quantify in monetary or other equivalent terms. For instance, all partners involved have exploitation plans which are Assets that might be exposed to different risks and might have different characteristics (e.g. quantification). An example could be the academic exploitation of the project, i.e. its capability to support PhDs or thesis, etc.

Understanding that it is pointless to overemphasize these details, the core Risk Analysis and Contingency Plan described here will focus only on **NEANIAS direct outputs, such as software, services, content, data etc.**

The “total” value of the Assets will be assumed to be the total value of the project, though this is an oversimplification as damages beyond the value of the project could occur in specific cases.

3.2.2. Risk Analysis

3.2.2.1. Risk Identification

The first part of the methodology is about labelling the risks that the project is exposed to. The method in NEANIAS is that each task and collectively each workpackage of the project will identify the risks they perceive that the Assets that they are expected to deliver, or contribute to, are exposed to.

The labelling of the risks must identify:

- The **source / problem** of a risk, which can be anything external or internal to the project that behaves outside the margins it is expected to behave. Typically, these margins should be settled by the specifications; however, these are not those that are of interest to our Risk Analysis, but rather the margins on which the Plan of the project has been settled on. Multiple sources logically combined can form one risk.
- The **target / impact** which is always internal to the project. Target can be any element of NEANIAS that is affected by a source / problem while the impact is the problem raised in the target, expressed in qualitative and/or quantitative manner.

Those need to be stated in a subject and additional note describing a risk in a short yet narrative manner which makes further analysis feasible.

As initial indicators,

- The **probability** of the appearance of the risk can also be attached as an initial step
- The **relative impact** sizing at the project level may be indicated in coarse terms

however, those are quite probable to be reconsidered at the analysis stage.

Under the above-mentioned approach, implementation members and task leaders will identify low level risks and their impact, while Work package and management leadership will identify higher level risks.

3.2.2.2. Risk Evaluation

Based on the findings of Risk Identification, each and every risk identified has to be evaluated.

The **Probability** for a particular risk to be met is the first of the two main metrics of our risk evaluation. Although probability should be ranging from 0 to 1, since there are no formulas to define it nor enough experimental data are there for the majority of the risks, it is not easily quantifiable and other means need to be employed for its approximation.

The **Impact** is the second metric of an identified risk and it offers the measure of the damage that will be caused to the targeted element in case of appearance of the risk. This is also not easily quantifiable, especially in an absolute form that would allow risks to be compared across the project.

This is a typical case in IT project and the workaround is quite common: probability is estimated by indirect methods such as “expert” opinions, offers, negotiations etc. NEANIAS will depend on “expert” opinions that label the risks.

However, NEANIAS will not adopt the terms of Impact and Probability but rather the terms of **Probability Rank** and **Impact Rank** which are more appropriate. Probability Rank liberates the analysis from the strict mathematical terms, while Impact Rank allows one to add a degree of freedom and use indirect reference to “absolute” costs of risk appearance.

Probability Rank		Impact Rank	
Description	Value	Description	Value
None	0	Does not essentially affect NEANIAS	0
Low	1	Affect NEANIAS in missing a secondary objective (e.g. inferior quality of a service or a deliverable)	1
Medium	2	Affects NEANIAS in missing a secondary objective (e.g. failure to deliver a service or a deliverable) or has a minor impact on several objectives.	2
High	5	Affects NEANIAS in missing multiple significant deliverables or services.	5
Certain	10	The maximum impact that may be considered, potentially affecting partners name	10

Table 3.1: Probability and Impact values.

3.2.2.3. Risk Classification

Risk Classification is the main part of risk analysis. Having the value of the Assets that are exposed to the risk, the indicator of likelihood of the risk and the potential impact this will have, one can estimate the importance of the risk which is typically measured by the term **Risk Exposure**. Risk Exposure is mathematically calculated as the product of Probability by Impact; thus, we will not use the same term. Instead we will use **Risk Exposure Ranking** or Simply **Ranking**, which can be calculated either simply as the product of the two rankings or via a third table which maps the Probability and Impact Rankings to Risk Exposure Rankings.

The methodology expects that all risks are collected under a common terminology (as already adopted), aligned and homogenized by a single Quality Assurance and Risk Management board and finally are refined to expose errors in estimations or cascading effects those risks may have.

- Duplicate removal as several actors may be observing the same rising risk.
- Analysis and break down of risk elements into additional ones (i.e. sources, impacts) that may be triggering or cascading effects of a particular risk.
- Homogenization of quantification and terminology across risks. This allows that cross-references among risks can be identified and taken into account.
- Sorting of risks according to the source / problem is the next step, so that the often-occurring ones, with multiple effects, can be grouped in one element with the total Risk Exposure Ranking and multiple targets / impacts.

At this point both considered approaches will be adopted:

- First sort the risks under the Exposure Ranking so that the most serious problems can be identified and selected for mitigation.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Then sort the risks under their Probability Rank allowing identify the ones most likely to emerge and then investigate the chains they might be triggering.

A third alternative that would involve resolution of cascading effects, could potentially be investigated in simpler ecosystems; however, in NEANIAS, the complexity of interdependencies prohibits such an exercise.

The highest-ranking risks under the two approaches, will be the ones identified as system risks and their environment will be described in detail, with regards to:

- Triggering of the risk
- Impact on a qualitative description
- Impact on cost / time equivalents

The list of the highest-ranking lists will be further analysed by project experts to reason on the need to be mitigated with any potential impact on partners' costs and work and shall be presented to the project for further handling.

3.2.3. Risk Control

3.2.3.1. Planning

The reasoning behind the Risk Analysis is to ultimately allow control of the risks of a project / system. Risk Control is the process that allows one to be continuously aware of, and able to react to, risks surrounding the Project. It is not a "once-off" of procedure but a task that has to be constantly active. A consistent plan is adopted and is set to be followed by assigned people throughout the duration of the project.

This plan involves:

- setting responsibilities for managing the plan itself
- performing periodical updates of the plan
- training on aspects of the plan such as a particular risk's resolution process etc.
- the process for monitoring risks
- the process for resolving risks

Planning also sets the enriched set of information that needs to be gathered and analyzed as part of Risk Analysis. For each risk it assumes all the elements mentioned in Risk Analysis elements, yet the need for elaborate description is essential for planning the monitoring and mitigation of a risk.

- A full description of the Risk that includes
 - Source / Problem
 - Impact in qualitative terms
 - Situation under which it might occur, perhaps even in a complex logical combination of events
 - Linked risks
- Means to monitor the appearance and evolution of the risk
- Means to handle the risk upon its appearance
- Responsible(s) for monitoring the risk and responsible(s) for handling the risk, which might differ.
- A timeline (in months) for periodic (or next) re-evaluation of a risk.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

According to the methodology, a single list is constructed containing all the details of a risk analysis that is periodically.

3.2.3.2. Mitigation

Risk Mitigation may refer to the reduction of the Impact Ranking of a risk, which may be either reduction of the probability to emerge or reduction of the impact it might have on project's Assets. It has to be noted though, that a mitigation strategy does not target the nullification of a risk's appearance probability or full elimination of the impact the risk might cause, since this might be practically infeasible or of disproportional cost. The overall objective of mitigation is the optimal handling of risks, i.e. balancing resources utilized for prevention with the impact expected.

This means that Risk Mitigation might refer to either or both of handling a risk before it is materialized on the Assets of the project or recovering from the damages caused by a risk.

Mitigation itself might be referring to

With regards to Risk Mitigation, upon there are a number of strategies that are applicable to NEANIAS, which are enumerated below:

- Evade the risk by eliminating the probability of its triggering events
- Evade the risk by eliminating its connection with the project
- Transfer of the risk impact to another party or entity (e.g. insurance)
- Accept the risk without countermeasures
- Accept the risk with late reaction (i.e. fix issues after the impact initially occurs)
- Exploit risk's side effects for balancing the impact

One aspect of Risk Analysis is to identify the proper strategy for each risk.

3.2.3.3. Monitoring

An effective way of Risk Monitoring is the continuous update of the TOP-n ranking risks of the project. It not only refers to Risks that may emerge and are not yet handled, but also ones that are under execution of countermeasures either for prevention or for reaction to their impact. It requires systematic update of all the relevant contributions (be it description, estimation or evaluation) so that the ranked list is well maintained and reasoned. This can be an effort/time-consuming process, which imposes an additional project cost that needs to be incorporated to risk management impact. Fortunately, enough, if applied consistently, periodically and in a differential manner, the procedure becomes quite straightforward and can be supported by non-expert actors in Risk Management, such as the workforce of a Research and Innovation Action, as part of their regular activities.

Monitoring is a multi-pass process that engages all processes of Risk Analysis and Risk Planning. It first triggers the update of the risks' list and then, according to the Risk Classification strategy, the risks that score the top rankings enter the further analysis and planning stage. Newcomers i.e. risks that make it to the top rankings for the first time are also subject to further analysis. Risks departing from the list's top-ranking entries, due to either project's mitigation actions or external factors, are also further analysed for further action planning.

For this purpose, for each risk, the following information is used:

- Current Position in the Top-n ranking
- Previous Position in the Top-n ranking

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Risk description
- Risk status and progress towards resolution (if applicable)

3.3. Procedures & Responsibilities

NEANIAS adopts the following Procedures and responsibilities for Risk Control.

3.3.1. Planning

The following are the key elements of the Risk Planning process:

- Risk Planning is performed by QAT, led by the QA Manager.
- The team periodically, approximately on an **eight (8) month** basis, reconsiders the risk plan for potential updates and announces those to the project. The activity starts at **M3** of the project, with an initial list of risk presented as part of this Report. Risk Plan updates are presented to the PMB which may present those to the GA depending on their contents.
- **Continuous update process:** PMB monitors and updates risks list on a monthly basis as part of the regular PMB meetings with adhoc information flows. Project Manager is responsible for indicating new risks to QAT for further analysis, via QA Manager who is also member of the PMB. QAT will assign responsible(s) outside QAT for further risk analysis.
- **Periodic update process:** Risk Analysis is performed on a quarterly basis with the support of PMB and the information provided in structured form in periodic reports.
- Key persons from project's workforce (non QAT members) are candidates for **monitoring risks** that are under observation. QAT performs an initial assignment which may be revised by PMB.
- Key persons and their organisations are assigned the execution of **mitigation actions** of selected risks identified for handling. Assignments are performed by QAT either on a personal or institutional basis. PMB validates the assignments and if needed elevates the decision to GA.
- PMB (and consequently the GA) may exceptionally undertake action on any risk not unreasonably **overriding** QAT indications and Risk Management processes.

Planning process assumes the following information is maintained per risk, which is supplied by various stages of Risk Control activities. It also coarsely refers to stages mostly responsible for delivering the relevant information.

Table 3.2: Risk information gathered

Column	Description	Stage
ID	A unique identifier for each risk.	Planning / Monitoring
Observed	The date the risk is observed	Planning / Monitoring
Last Update	The date the last update of the risk was performed	Planning / Monitoring
Reporter	Person / Partner that reports the risk	Planning / Monitoring

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Column	Description	Stage
Responsible (Monitoring)	The person(s) responsible for the monitoring of the risk	Planning / Monitoring
Responsible (Mitigation)	The person(s) responsible for the mitigating of the risk	Planning / Monitoring
Evaluation Period (Months)	The period that this risk requires re-evaluation, in months.	Planning / Monitoring
WPs	Workpackages involved in risk.	Planning / Monitoring
Source / Problem	The source/problem of the risk, serving also as a title of the risk	Planning / Monitoring
Impact	The impact of the risk as a short statement	Planning / Monitoring
Description	The full description of the risk in a narrative manner that allows the reader to comprehend triggering and cascading effects as well as to evaluate the impact and probability of the risk.	Planning / Monitoring
Mitigation Strategy	General mitigation strategy of the risk among the ones selected for the project: Evade risk (Eliminate source/probability) Evade risk (Disconnect project) Transfer risk Accept the risk Accept risk with late reaction Accept risk and exploit side effects	Risk Analysis
Mitigation	Mitigation strategy for the particular risk, in a narrative manner that allows one to identify proper assignments and timeline for the mitigation.	Risk Analysis
Probability Rank	Probability rank as presented by methodology: - None - Low - Medium - High - Certain	Risk Analysis
Impact Rank	Impact rank as presented by methodology: - None - Low - Medium	Risk Analysis

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Column	Description	Stage
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High - Certain 	
Risk Exposure Ranking	Calculated Risk Exposure Ranking (Probability X Impact)	Risk Analysis
Previous Ranking	Risk Exposure Ranking of the risk in the previous evaluation, in order to identify rising or dropping risks.	Monitoring
Status	Status of risk handling: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluation - No action - Prevention action - Recovery action - Eliminated 	Planning / Monitoring / Mitigation
Cascading Effects (triggers)	Any links to other risks that may be triggered by this risk in case of materialization.	Risk Analysis

The data are collected on project's workspace via an online shared document managed by the QAT and contributed by all PMB members.

3.3.2. Mitigation

The following are key elements of the Risk Mitigation process and responsibilities.

- Risk Mitigation is handled by appointed persons and their organisations.
- Risk Mitigation assignments may be suggested by QAT, the PMB holding the decision role.
- Once a risk exceeds a level of Impact Ranking the GA may override any prior decision on risk handling and resort to completely different means for the Mitigation strategy and assignments.
- Mitigation process is monitored on a monthly (PMB meetings) and quarterly (Activity Progress Report) basis. All actions taken on Risk Mitigation shall be reported in the Quarterly Activity Progress Report.
- Partners shall be instructed by PMB and subsequently the GA to engage external (i.e. non project) resources for mitigating risks that may arise for the project Assets due to their organizational, technical or scientific shortcomings.

3.3.3. Monitoring

As stated in Risk Planning section, monitoring is performed in two frequencies, monthly and quarterly. The elements of Risk Monitoring are summarized below:

- Risk monitoring is based around the maintenance of the Risk Monitoring List established in the project. QAT supervises the update of the list.
- Monthly risk monitoring list update is performed in regular PMB meetings. During the meetings specific risks may be identified for out-of-process handling.
- Quarterly risk monitoring list update is performed along regular activity progress reporting by Workpackage Leaders, using information gathered from Task Leaders.

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

- Risk analysis is performed on a quarterly basis unless exceptionally triggered by PMB findings.
- Risks ranking changes (i.e. newly highly ranked risks or dropping ranking risks) are identified by QAT.
- Assignments of mitigation responsible persons (or organisations) per risk are performed as part of monitoring once risk ranking changes are suggested by QAT. PMB may override – not unreasonably - any such assignment.
- Assignments of risk monitoring responsible persons are suggested by QAT. PMB may override – not unreasonably - such assignments.

3.3.4. Residual risk

Residual Risk is risk that remains for project assets, after all risk mitigation measures have been applied. Residual risk mitigation is usually a risk control measure for a higher-level risk management enclosing where the project may be a component of. A common top-level measure for mitigating residual risk is to financially insure the assets of the project, however this is not a common practice in Research and Innovation Action projects.

In the context of the NEANIAS, any residual risk will be mitigated by associated partners with any or both of the two following approaches:

1. Time extension of the project
2. Effort extension of the project

Note: Any offloading of such planning to individual Partner internal risk management processes is expected yet not analysed in the context of NEANIAS Risk Management planning.

3.4. Identified Risks

The following table presents a list of risks that persist or arise at the time of the Report. In the remainder of the project, the project workforce will take actions to minimize the probability rank or impact rank of the risks that can be controlled.

It has to be noted that the

- Impact Rank refers to impact remaining after any corrective actions taken against risks that may have already appeared and not their initial Impact Rank.
- As “Certain” appear risks that have already appeared and persist to this point of the project.
- Several other risks have been eliminated as results of the project have occurred and have already been evaluated and matched their objectives
- Other risks have been demoted as the reasons or timing for their appearance is no longer present.

Table 3.3: Current (M31) Top Ranking Identified Risks

Last update	WPs	Source Problem /	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
30/5/2022	WP10	The COVID pandemic impacts the ability to organize and participate in events, as well	COVID-19 is strongly affecting the possibility of making trips, trips and face-to-face meetings, which makes it difficult to organize or participate in events,	It is a global problem, and the risk cannot be avoided. The mitigation plan is to organize and attend digital events (webinars, online conferences, online	Certain	Medium	20

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Last update	WPs	Source / Problem	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
		as attract the audience.	fairs, exhibitions, congresses, etc. Impact: Dissemination activities distortion.	exhibitions, online presentations)			
30/5/2022	WP4; WP6	Delay in timely recruiting research personnel due to coronavirus	Recruitment processes have been delayed due to coronavirus, specifically: 1) administration personnel overloaded with out-of-office tasks, 2) difficult to contact interested people to apply for the post, 3) selection process takes longer due to remote meetings of the interviewing/selecting panels to evaluate the candidates. Impact: Project plan distortion.	Revision of implementation plan and extension of activities until the end of the project.	Certain	Medium	20
3/3/2020	All (WP1; WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7; WP8; WP9; WP10)	Pandemic General Threat to performing project activities in several areas	Coronavirus threatens progress of activity in several directions, as affecting physical meetings and collaboration, common time availability, sick leaves or leaves related to the virus, etc, that all these may lead to deliverables/tasks delays Impact: Project plan distortion.	Partners' have the needed experience and the required tools for working and collaborating remotely and the project has already set collaboration tools specifically for the project (workspace, ticketing, messaging, etc). In case of temporal network issues on main conference or messaging tools of the project, other online available systems will be temporally used. Revising time plan will be needed. KPIs might require shifting to other priorities.	Certain	Low	10
9/7/2020	WP2;	Problems accessing NEANIAS Infrastructure Resources (e.g. Cloud, GitHub etc)	Problems delivering infrastructure (cloud and other) resources may hinder development plan of operation infrastructure. This may refer to testing or production environment. The effect is delaying development or hindering quality of service offered by the	Alternative infrastructures will be sought and utilized. Delay to the development plan will be applied where needed.	Certain	Low	10

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Last update	WPs	Source / Problem	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
			partners. Impact: Project plan distortion.				
18/5/2021	WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7	Resource availability not matching service usage requirements	Some services, by nature or by input volume are demanding high resource availability (storage and/or compute) that may not be matched through available infrastructure resources Impact: Reduced service adoption.	In the process of delivering the NEANIAS service offerings, one of the key aspects to be addressed is to optimally allocate the available resources. For the purpose, the available partner infrastructures are utilized to separate resource utilization based on usage kind (development, testing, staging, production) and service consumption (internal, external). Still, some services, by nature or by input volume are demanding high resource availability (storage and/or compute). To this end, contingencies need to be investigated, and plans made to continue supporting the level of quality NEANIAS services are targeting.	High	Medium	10
30/5/2022	All (WP1; WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7; WP8; WP9; WP10)	KPIs achievement	Depending on several factors (such as the pandemic and the revision of implementation plan) KPIs achievement may be impacted. Impact: Project performance distortion.	Other KPIs that are not impacted could be stressed further. As for WP10, the impossibility of achieving some KPIs would be compensated by promoting other achievements as compensation, so that the general objectives of WP10 are also satisfied.	High	Medium	10
30/5/2022	WP8; KPIs	Delays to the onboarding of services on EOSC	The EOSC onboarding plans of service providers are not very clear. In the case of core services (C3 and C4) plans are still under investigation. Impact: Difficulty/ delays to meeting KPIs for services on EOSC. Increased effort for supporting/ facilitating EOSC onboarding activities.	Close monitoring of onboarding activities by WP8 partners. Regular communication with service providers for updates and support.	High	Medium	10
30/5/2022	WP8; WP2; WP3;	Missing or inadequate statements of Terms of Use,	The terms and the policies under which NEANIAS services can be used have not been	Preparation of "templates" for Terms of Use and Privacy Policy that can be customised	High	Medium	10

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Last update	WPs	Source / Problem	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
	WP4; WP6	Access Policy and Privacy Policy for NEANIAS services	defined by service providers nor plans for their preparation exist (apart from a few services). Impact: Potential users of the services will not know under which terms the services are offered. Non-compliance to GDPR. Such documents will soon (July 2022) become mandatory for services on EOSC.	by NEANIAS service providers. Support of service providers by WP8 during preparation of the documents. Close monitoring of the issue by WP8 partners. Regular communication with service providers for follow-up and support.			
30/5/2022	WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7;	Delivery of low-quality outcomes (mainly software components of services)	Service quality may suffer from usability, stability, performance, accuracy and several other issues. Impact: Reduced service adoption.	Consortium members have a strong record of 100% successful project completion. Provider SMEs have a similar record in commercial projects. Agile methodology adopted along with assessment and evaluation being integral processes of project further mitigate the risk. All partners, esp ones with leading roles engage experienced, senior personnel in such activities.	Low	High	5
30/5/2022	WP8	EOSC Marketplace does not have pay-for-use ordering, or any other financial transaction support in its roadmap	Some of the thematic services require big capacity machines for use cases that go beyond certain input size. Pay-for-use could be an option for those use cases to recuperate the cost of using big machines. Additionally, some of the thematic service providers are commercial entities and would like to provide their service on a pay-for-use basis in EOSC. Impact: Inability of the thematic service providers to provide their service on a pay-for-use basis .	The pay-for-use ordering cannot be elaborated further in NEANIAS. The providers who need this option should register their service with a 'demonstration access' level in EOSC. More complex access has to be negotiated bilaterally with the user outside EOSC/NEANIAS.	High	Low	5
30/5/2022	WP5;	Delays to the onboarding of innovation cases to NEANIAS	Due to several factors, such as complexity of the process, the pandemic, the status of implementation	The project shall revise its timeline of the respective activities and will try to build links to innovation cases so that	High	Low	5

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Last update	WPs	Source / Problem	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
			etc. it is quite probable that the entire vision of the project regarding innovation cases might not be carried out. This will impact the abilities to build synergies, sustainability supporting links and validate the services from an external user perspective. Impact: Reduced validation and exploitation of services.	they can continue exploiting NEANIAS offerings beyond the project's time line. Innovation cases are not the sole means of services' validation and as such may allow			
30/5/2022	WP2; WP3; WP4;	Poor community engagement for the execution of research sector case.	Services might not meet their target group's adoption expectation for a wide range of reasons, which includes competition, evolution of the landscape, technological challenges and other factors. As a result users of the cases may not be adequately interested to exploit the services for their cause. Impact: Reduced service adoption.	Research sector cases are well-defined addressing essential needs and their initial research sector is already included in the project directly and not through intermediaries. Additional and alternative communities and user channels are being attracted with new activities that counterfight the effects of the plan shifting due to the pandemic.	Medium	Medium	4
30/5/2022	WP7;	Dedicated support team	As interconnections between services increase and service boundaries are crossed to facilitate individual service offerings, issues reported require cross service and cross partner involvement to identify problems and resolutions Impact: Reduced quality outcomes.	To properly support service uptake and as usage of the services and their interconnections increase, it is becoming necessary to establish a cross partner task group to act as the first line of support for incidents reported, requiring additional effort allocation.	Medium	Medium	4
30/5/2022	WP5;	Organisation of innovation workshop, open innovation aspects	Open innovation workshops should be organised in order to develop the services with the involvement of the end-users. The first workshop was planned for June, but for the unavailability of thematic sector	The appropriate timing should be scheduled for September 2022.	Medium	Medium	4

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Last update	WPs	Source / Problem	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
			representatives, it is postponed until September. Impact: Development of services in align with the needs of the end-user.				
30/5/2022	WP7;	Insufficient SLA for meeting user requirements	SLA terms provided by the project partners may not meet expectancies or requirements of user communities Impact: Reduced service adoption.	SLA terms shall be elaborated early in the project so that users are made early aware of those and any limitations in order to identify workarounds and/or synergies for mitigating the risk.	Medium	Low	2
30/5/2022	WP2; WP3; WP4;	TRL of existing thematic sector services and components does not meet the expectancies of the users	Detailed evaluation of TRL of components giving birth to thematic services may yield lower TRL levels than initially estimated. Impact: Reduced service adoption.	The primary counter measure is the extension of allocated effort from internal responsible partner resources, to confront any issues with the TRL identified by its users. In case of infeasibility of reaching the service to an adequate TRL level, the service will be omitted from EOSC service offerings. As additional services are expected to emerge from the project, this most probably will not affect the KPIs of the project.	Low	Medium	2
30/5/2022	WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7	Resources sustainability (post project)	Not all partners have secured the availability of resources for continuous support and operation of the services beyond project's timeline. This might be due to the evolving labour status in the research and IT domains, or due to the high cost of infrastructure resources coming from power, cooling, hardware etc. Impact: Hindered sustainability.	The project accepts the risk and tries to find additional sources of resources for mid/long term sustainability of resource, adding up to resources that are already secured by partners, minimizing the extent and impact of the risk.	Medium	Low	2

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

The following was the initial list of highest ranked identified risks at the time of the report: Table 3.4: Initial Top Ranking Identified Risks

Observed	WPs	Source / Problem	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
23/12/2019	WP6;	New core services and components arise, not planned in the DOA	Analysis of user requirements and NEANIAS architecture may lead to needs for new services and components. Impact: Reduced service achievements	Technology partners already have assets that may cover additional needs. Furthermore, the EOSC and RI landscape may offer solutions to quite a few unplanned technological component requirements. As a last resort technology partners may have to realign their effort to cover additional requirements re-prioritizing their contribution, while additional effort is already committed by few partners.	Medium	High	10
23/12/2019	WP7;	Insufficient SLA for meeting user requirements	SLA terms provided by the project partners may not meet expectancies or requirements of user communities Impact: Reduced service adoption	SLA terms shall be elaborated early in the project so that users are made early aware of those and any limitations in order to identify workarounds and/or synergies for mitigating the risk.	Medium	High	10
30/11/2019	WP2; WP3; WP4;	TRL of existing thematic sector services and components does not meet the expectancies of the users	Detailed evaluation of TRL of components giving birth to thematic services may yield lower TRL levels than initially estimated. Impact: Reduced service adoption	The primary counter measure is the extension of allocated effort from internal responsible partner resources, to confront any issues with the TRL identified by its users. In case of infeasibility of reaching the service to an adequate TRL level, the service will be omitted from EOSC service offerings. As additional services are expected to emerge from the project, this most probably will not affect the KPIs of the project.	High	Medium	10
21/1/2019	All (WP1; WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7; WP8; WP9; WP10)	Lack of a required expertise / competence for the success of the project or tasks.	Impact: Reduced quality outcomes	The choice of participants assures full coverage of the landscape of expertise required in the project. Furthermore, the synthesis covers the potential need to strengthen a sector with contribution from other partners, while liaison activities will be fostering synergies that mitigate such risk.	Low	High	5
21/1/2019	All (WP1; WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7; WP8; WP9; WP10)	Delivery of low-quality outcomes and mainly software components of services.	Impact: Reduced service adoption	Consortium members have a strong record of 100% successful project completion. Provider SMEs have a similar record in commercial projects. Agile methodology adopted along with assessment and evaluation being integral processes of project further mitigate the risk. All partners, esp ones with leading roles engage experienced, senior personnel in such activities.	Low	High	5
21/1/2019	WP2; WP3; WP4;	Poor community engagement for the execution of research sector case.	Impact: Reduced service adoption	Research sector cases are well-defined addressing essential needs and their initial research sector is already included in the project directly and no through intermediaries. Nevertheless, additional and alternative communities are identified and contacted to supplement pre-selected ones and strong engagement and capacity building	Low	High	5

D1.3 - Quality Assurance & Risk Management Plan - M31 Update

Observed	WPs	Source / Problem	Description / Impact	Mitigation	Probability Rank	Impact Rank	Ranking
				activities are foreseen, which further mitigate the risk.			
21/1/2019	WP9;	Business planning pointing to commercially unsustainable technologies	Impact: Reduced sustainability	As the outcome of business planning cannot be prejudged, Open Innovation calls try to expand the vision of the project on business cases. Partners will contribute to identify all potential by-products, alternative business opportunities, and other financing and sustainability options in order to locate all options leading to a sustainable result.	High	Low	5
30/11/2019	All (WP1; WP2; WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7; WP8; WP9; WP10)	M2 deliverables timeline	Deadline of first deliverables is overlapping with the period that many partners will not be operating and is too early in the project to modify it. Impact: Project plan distortion	The basic and indicative structure and content of the deliverables needs to be initially presented to partners prior to the deadline, so that any dependencies are internally resolved. The review process will be shortened in order to minimize any delay. Delay shall be communicated to the EC and shall be kept minimal (i.e. less than 30 calendar days).	High	Low	5

References

- [1] Project Workspace: <https://workspace.neanias.eu/>
- [2] Project management platform: <https://ticketing.neanias.eu/>

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PM	Project Manager
PMB	Project Management Board
QA	Quality Assurance
QAT	Quality Assurance and Risk Management Team
SSC	Scientific Steering Committee
TM	Technical Manager
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WG	Working Group